

Cryptocurrency and Financial Inclusion: Assessing the Impact on Banking Access and Economic
Growth in El Salvador's Underbanked Regions with a Focus on SMEs

Apr 12, 2024

Word Count: 5355

Introduction

The rise and further integration of cryptocurrencies have transformed the global financial landscape. This rise and integration are specifically in response to the COVID-19 pandemic that occurred over the past few years. El Salvador, a country with a total estimated population of 6.6 million people, is often referred to as the country with the highest rates and is known to have prevalent criminal gangs (CIA, 2024). However, despite these challenges, El Salvador has boldly emerged as a pioneer in adopting Bitcoin as its legal tender. Bitcoin is a cryptocurrency that is a digital currency on a blockchain network run by miners who solve complicated math problems. This groundbreaking move was prompted by the successful experiment of using cryptocurrency for transactions between businesses in El Zonte, a small nearby village in El Salvador (Nugent, 2021). The government's decision to adopt Bitcoin as legal tender alongside the U.S. dollar, used since 2001, marks a significant shift in financial inclusion and banking access within its under- or often-unbanked regions. These actions, driven by the current President, Nayib Buckle, have initiated a transition towards digital currency with promising things such as fees, expanding financial services, and further positioning itself as a hub of innovation (Sparkes, 2021).

Understanding cryptocurrency and its modern role in finance is essential. The entire market is worth around 2.25 trillion USD, with Bitcoin, the top cryptocurrency, worth 62,000 USD per coin as of April 13, 2024, and having a market cap of around 1.25 trillion USD (CoinMarketCap, 2024). The market cap of cryptocurrencies is often subject to fluctuations, underscoring their volatility and showcasing their growing significance in financial markets, comparable to top stocks and bonds. Cryptocurrencies such as Bitcoin have a crucial role in the evolution of financial technologies, offering quicker and cheaper transactions in regions often

limited to banking access (Gernster, 2022). Digital currencies, operating on blockchain technology, are decentralized ledgers that hold all records of transactions across networks, reduce costs, and help enhance security while including transparency, unlike traditional financial systems. It is vital to get insight into these digital assets as they have the potential to play a role in the future of finance.

Cryptocurrency has promised many individuals in El Salvador to aid them with access to financial services not included in traditional banking systems across the country. Almost 70% of Salvadorians (Name that refers to someone nationally from El Salvador) lack access to conventional bank accounts, and often, remittance includes an impactful portion of the GDP (Gross Domestic Product), leading to a potential role for digital currencies to impact the entire country's economic layout (Scientific American, 2022). There is a significant push towards this, evaluated by the nation's commitments to this potential change, evident with substantial investments into the crypto market as a whole when comparing it to the total budget of the country, demonstrating the importance of cryptocurrency in their future economic plans (Stinson, 2021). The situation El Salvador is currently experiencing, pursuing financial modernization via cryptocurrency, has broader implications for El Salvador's overall economic balance. The country faces macroeconomic issues, such as high public debt tied to the need for new creditors, which complicates the relationship between the country, its citizens, and the International Monetary Fund (Nugent, 2022). In this navigation through complex and adventurous waters, the adoption of Bitcoin has situated and stirred a mix of concern, hope, and critique (Argente et al., 2021). The integration of cryptocurrency has given many Salvadorans an opportunity to participate in global financial markets and systems that had often disregarded them, keeping

them on the bench. This is a step that allows them to create something that residents refer to as “Bitcoin Beach,” often being referenced as the “Salvadoran Dream,” similar to “The American Dream,” showcasing aspects of economic aspirations, achievements, and autonomy. However, such visions with infinite possibilities do not come without a significant amount of risk; the unknown, volatile nature of cryptocurrency can pose a considerable threat to El Salvador's Financial Stability, posing issues of its balance in the country's economic landscape (Rodriguez, 2022). Such risks often lead to concern, but there is a new wave of enthusiasm coming from the international crypto community, who were interested in the experiment in El Zone, which was initiated by a 100,000\$ donation to a local NGO; any of these individuals view the experiment as a groundbreaking model that could help to a pave an ideation and broader adoption of digital currencies such as Bitcoin (Buckele, 2021).

The research question that guides this research and that we will explore and evaluate is: How is the rise of cryptocurrency transforming financial inclusion and banking access in El Salvador's underbanked regions, and what are its broader implications for the country's economic landscape? This question is further explored with the sub-question exploring specifics: How does cryptocurrency adoption affect small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in El Salvador, particularly regarding credit and business growth opportunities, compared to previously used traditional banking systems? These questions will serve as the backbone of our research, guiding our exploration and evaluation of the impact of cryptocurrency adoption in El Salvador.

Literature Review

This literature review will explore and evaluate cryptocurrency's transformative impact on financial inclusion and banking access in El Salvador, mainly focusing on Bitcoin's adoption

as a legal tender. In this examination, light is not only shed upon the socioeconomic changes within El Salvador. Additionally, it contributes to the broader understanding of cryptocurrency and its ability to enhance and refine financial systems in underbanked regions. The emergence of Bitcoin as a legal tender in Salvador represents a sizable shift in the financial landscape, this once again being tied into enhancing financial inclusion, working on improvements such as reducing remittance fees, due to it being vital given that remittances constitute a significant portion of the country's GDP. This is an initiative that leverages Bitcoin to allow Salvadorans, notably the many 70% without bank accounts, to enable them to engage in financial activities and access many services that they were not previously provided due to being out of reach in traditional banking systems (Martinez, 2021). However, the rollout of this policy has not been without a significant number of challenges. Many technical issues with the development of a state-led wallet called Chivo Wallet, and over the volatility of Bitcoin itself, have raised a sizeable amount of concerns and resistance from the local population, often with a majority concerned with the stability and reliability of using cryptocurrencies as a standard means of day-to-day transactions (Alvarez et al., 2023). Alongside this, it is evident that there is a significant amount of resistance from the local population, with a majority expressing skepticism about the overall integration of Bitcoin into their entire economy (Taylor, 2021).

Despite all these significant challenges, the government of El Salvador, with President Nayib Bukele, has asserted that the adoption of Bitcoin will help reduce transaction fees for millions of people, amounting to billions of dollars in remittances, thereby providing economic relief and less economic strain on several families (Sparkes, 2021). The policy that supports this aims to position El Salvador as a leader in financial innovation, having personalities that would

attract global crypto entrepreneurs, investors, and enthusiasts interested in such a regulated but open economic landscape environment (Aquino, 2021). Looking more closely and in-depth, we can see the critical potential of Bitcoin to facilitate greater financial inclusion in a mixed way, with the risks associated with both volatility and the broader implications that it can instill on El Salvador's economy and economic landscape. For example, the International Monetary Fund and other financial analysts have voiced significant concern regarding macroeconomic stability and, more importantly, the lack of transparency in cryptocurrency transactions when things such as wallet addresses and information are withheld (Scientific American, 2022). This literature review can underscore the mixed outcomes of cryptocurrency adoption in El Salvador and evaluate its ability in such a market. The adoption and further implementation of cryptocurrency, such as bitcoin, offers an innovative approach to financial inclusion and one that can approach economic growth, particularly in underbanked regions. As stated before, this poses a significant financial risk and showcases many concerns about its ability to remain stable. This debate with many different opinions from countries to shape policies and perspectives on the use of digital currencies in developing countries is being reviewed in other countries such as India, South Africa, and the Philippines. This examination shows a critical contribution to understanding the complex dynamic between technological innovations in finance and their real-world implication on socioeconomic structures as a whole.

In this literature review, there is a deep underscore of a substantial gap that previous literature did not review in understanding the long-term economic outcomes of cryptocurrency adoption in developing countries such as El Salvador. Notably, understanding the effects of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and rural populations has this effect. Most available

research looks at the adoption of cryptocurrency and rates, starting with initial research on the challenges faced, often disregarding and thereby engaging a holistic evaluation of enduring economic effects alongside such financial technology's socio-economic/socio-cultural integration. This research endeavor aims to evaluate the facets, focusing especially intensely on SMEs in El Salvador's underbanked areas as they transition from traditional or unbanked situations to using and adopting cryptocurrency. This inspection is critically essential as SMEs significantly boost economic development in regions that this shift might impact. A deeper dive into an investigation is also critical to understanding the social and cultural dynamics of financial-technology(FinTech) adoption to better shed light on how innovations such as Bitcoin can be integrated and further adopted into different environments.

Methodology

Introduction to Methodological Path

In this methodology, many different topics will be evaluated to dissect the complex effect of cryptocurrency integration on financial inclusion, understanding the complexities of its adoption in the broader scheme of its economic landscape and its impact on SMEs across the country. To evaluate the complex topic above, we will focus on a Mixed-Method approach to explain the range of topics. This methodology articulates a combination of qualitative content and quantitative data analyses, thus giving a more comprehensive understanding of the topics researched and furthering our understanding of the ability to integrate digital currencies such as Bitcoin into a country's economy. Using such a blend of these methodologies, the study aims to capture a nuanced socio-economic impact while maintaining and adhering to all necessary ethical research practices. Gbadebo described using volume and price as a suitable method of

correlation to understand crypto and used data analysis to evaluate the data further (Gbadebo, 2023). In this paper, they understood the correlation. They concluded the relationship between the price and volume, which they could further back up their claim with research found online on reputable databases.

Detailed Research Design

Using such a methodological framework, it will be divided into two interconnected components: Content Analysis and Data Analysis, both of which lead to a Mixed-Method research methodology. Looking at the Qualitative aspect, Content Analysis involves a systematic examination of a range of relevant academic literature, media reports, and official documents. These will all be found carefully using academically recognized databases such as EBSCO host, Coin Based Website (CoinMarketCap et al., etc.), or Google Scholar, ensuring that only a good range of high-quality and trusted information is provided. This approach allows us to get an in-depth exploration of the narratives and discussion surrounding the role cryptocurrency has in foisting financial inclusion in a country such as El Salvador; similarly, the quantitative component, Data Analysis, involves understanding and evaluating statistical data, economic indicators, trends, charts, graphs, to get a range of information, such as the usage of cryptocurrency. Using such empirical investigation for this research will aim to quantify the macroeconomic effects of Bitcoin's adoption and further inauguration as a legal tender. Using a range of data and this methodology, the study will evaluate and further interpret the economic data, having the ability to draw comparisons with similar economic ways and consider how cryptocurrencies could work in such markets and look at it on a level for financial inclusion in

underbanked regions and understanding its impacts on SMEs to get the most effective context within global finance framework and landscape.

Comprehensive Sampling and Data Collection Strategy

For the qualitative analysis, a purposive sampling method will be utilized to curate a collection of documents that directly relate to the study's themes. Criteria for selection include the document's relevance to the impact of cryptocurrency on underbanked populations, its scholarly integrity, and the depth of its analysis concerning economic conditions in El Salvador. The aim is to encompass a broad spectrum of perspectives to ensure a balanced view of the subject matter. In qualitative research, data will be meticulously gathered from credible sources such as Yahoo Finance, Coinatmradar, and WorldPopulationReview. This data will encompass a range of indicators, including, but not limited to, financial inclusion rates, the volume of cryptocurrency transactions, and broad economic metrics post-adoption of Bitcoin. Going more into a step-by-step process, we can see the below for getting the data:

1. The first step is getting the data. We will first get data from Yahoo Finance on BTC-USD, ETH-USD, and META, and then get the CSV of the data from the date of Bitcoin adoption (September 7, 2021). After that, you will need to get the data from WorldPopulation Review and Coinatmradar and format it as City:Population: Atm; this can be stored in a file called atm.py in the dictionary.
2. Next, we will have to understand the data and how to use it; in this process, we usually clean it, but since some of the data was limited, there was no need for any cleaning.
3. Import the data into your code editor, such as Visual Studio Code (VSC), PyCharm, or Replit. For this research, I used VSC.

Advanced-Data Analysis Techniques

Quantitative data from the Data Analysis will undergo an evaluation of these sources and use a range of data to understand the research. The criteria and goal will be to get a theme and understanding of how cryptocurrencies fluctuate in price, compare them to other stocks, understand population to ATM, and compare with statistical analysis and more, which will be showcased step-by-step below:

1. Open Visual Studio Code and upload it with the 3 CSVs and a file called atm.py, which contains data formatted as a dictionary.
2. Next, make sure to install Python. I used Python 3.9, but many different versions will work.
3. Then, make sure you have all of the needed libraries. If not, run this command:
`'pip install numpy scipy pandas matplotlib seaborn statsmodels scikit-learn seaborn.'`
4. Once you have done the above, we will start the coding, which will have four different files for Python: atm.py, graphsall.py, method1.py, and method2.py.
5. In this, we will do statistical analysis with regression and correlation, aligned with comparative and predictive analysis.
6. Start by opening up atm.py. Now import pandas as pd and matplotlib.pyplot as plt, and make sure the dictionary (called data) is formatted as City:Population: ATMs. Next, we will create a data frame and add all the data and points, having a Bar for ATMs and a line chart for the population, in which each city (formatted by the Highest number of ATMs) will be listed below.

7. Next, we will graph the three CSV files, import the same things, seaborn, and create three different frames. Then, we will plot the data comparing Volume and Close (Price at the end of the day) prices for all days for each item and get three charts. We will also make a scatter plot comparing Close vs. Volume. We will produce six graphs and visualizations based on this.
8. Next is Model1.py, in which we will use a min regression model using analysis to examine the relationship between crypto and economic indicators such as SMEs growth and credit access in El Salvador. We will import the same as step 6 and statsmodels, in which our model will be added (constant intercept), and we will compare this with BTC Volume vs Close.
9. Finally, we look at Model2.py, in which we use sklearn (Mini-Machine Learning) and import it, and the same one from step 6. This will use the R-squared model, which is a linear regression model, and will be compared similarly to the BTC Volume vs Close. This will be a predictive model that predicts future trends and sees the economic implications that El Salvador may face using cryptocurrencies.

Ethical Considerations in Research

Ethical integrity is fundamental in this research paper, and following all guidelines is evident throughout the paper. All procedures for getting, finding, evaluating, and analyzing data will comply with ethical standards set by the Institutional Review Board (IRB). This paper will follow all rules and adhere to their policies. In this research, it will be stated that we will adhere to all ethical guidelines, and any use of data will follow all standards to give the best and most effective outcome, ensuring there are no issues and issues such as conflicts of interest, besides

the research paper. The statistics will be cited, and all information used to understand the topic will be mentioned in the bibliography. All information text will have in-text citations, etc. This research aims to get the most ethical outcome and report what occurs. The research will be transparent, and the methodology and findings, such as the above, will be reported to ethically and effectively contribute to the academic community and conversation.

Scholarly Contribution and Impact

This research is constructed and designed to fill a significant gap in the academic conversation and answer questions left out in the extended literature regarding the economic impacts of cryptocurrency in developing countries such as El Salvador, using SMEs as an example. With the ability to provide empirical data and detailed qualitative insights, this study aims to provide and contribute valuable knowledge to the ongoing debates in economics, fintech, and the entire crypto field. Considering the findings, they are expected to evaluate the potential for policies that are there and want to go forward with helping scholars in this academic conversation understand the potential of integrating cryptocurrency into the economic landscape.

Conclusion and Methodological Summary

This research is a Mixed-Method approach that can provide a comprehensive and nuanced perspective on the impacts of cryptocurrency adoption in El Salvador. By having this ability, it can combine both qualitative and quantitative research methods, which this study will ensure a balance of ethics and academic definition, having significant potential and future abilities to contribute to the field of economics and financial technology.

Results

Quantitative Analysis

Based on the results of the qualitative analysis, we have diverse perspectives on the impact of Bitcoin, and have been looking at it since its introduction. We looked over topics concerning financial inclusion, the operations of SMEs, and the broader economic implications of El Salvador's bold move.

Financial Inclusion

The integration of Bitcoin has focused on enhancing financial inclusion by providing unbanked populations with access to digital currency and financial services (Stephen, 2022). Government incentives help the adoption of the Chivo Wallet, a state-run ledger that gives a 30\$ Bitcoin credit; this gives citizens familiarity with cryptocurrency and its uses (Stephen, 2022). Regarding these efforts, many citizens have yet to have a favorable opinion of this new technology. Surveys indicate that a substantial amount of the population felt unprepared to use Bitcoin in everyday transactions, showcasing a significant gap between technological deployment and community readiness (Best, 2023). Many individuals cannot access ATMs, which is still difficult in underbanked areas. However, incentives and new integrations are increasing interest and financial inclusion within El Salvador, even though the public is unfavorable.

Impact on SMEs

SMEs are a crucial part of the integration of Bitcoin, and they present both opportunities and challenges. Often, it promised reduced transaction fees and quicker access to funds, making it easier to handle cash flow constraints (Engler, 2023). Nevertheless, the high volatility of Bitcoin raised concerns about its stability and its potential impact on businesses' ability to budget effectively and operate on a day-to-day basis. Moreover, the mandatory interrogation for

adopting Bitcoin imposed many issues due to new investments and training, which became a barrier for many, who often operate on thin margins (Rodriguez, 2024). Despite these challenges, SMEs are showing upsides to using Bitcoin, with easy payment and usage after the initial challenges in using Bitcoin for payment.

Broader Economic Implications

Looking at Bitcoin's implications on a macroeconomic level, we see that many individuals and financial institutions have closely watched its adoption. While some hailed it as a forward-thinking move that could position El Salvador as a leader in financial technology, others, including major financial entities like the IMF, expressed concerns about potential destabilizing effects due to Bitcoin's inherent volatility (Rodriguez, 2024). The widespread mistrust in Bitcoin's stability and its implications on inflation aligning with exchange rates has made it an issue within and beyond Salvador's borders to fully adopt it and rely on Bitcoin (Best, 2023).

Quantitative Analysis

We will review the data visualized from the methodology, which will help us get more information to answer the question. We will further understand a range of data points and graphs formulated above, and these are the visualization and understanding of the analyses we have done above in the methodology. These. These are the results of the analysis.

Price and Volume Since Adoption

Scatter Plot Volume Vs Price

Correlation Between Volume and Close (In order: BTC, ETH, META):

Correlation between Volume and Close: 0.30319903978685037

Correlation between Volume and Close: 0.4528203478822792

Correlation between Volume and Close: -0.3891862520200427

Comparing Regression and prediction, Statsmodel and Sklearn

R-squared: 0.09192965772766815

```

=====
                        OLS Regression Results
=====
Dep. Variable:          Close    R-squared:                0.092
Model:                 OLS      Adj. R-squared:           0.091
Method:                Least Squares
Date:                  Sun, 14 Apr 2024    F-statistic:              96.07
Time:                  11:13:40          Prob (F-statistic):       1.13e-21
No. Observations:     951              Log-Likelihood:           -10379.
Df Residuals:         949              AIC:                      2.076e+04
Df Model:              1                BIC:                      2.077e+04
Covariance Type:      nonrobust
=====
                    coef    std err          t      P>|t|      [0.025    0.975]
-----
const              2.61e+04    965.755     27.022    0.000    2.42e+04    2.8e+04
Volume             3.184e-07    3.25e-08     9.802    0.000    2.55e-07    3.82e-07
=====
Omnibus:              21.279    Durbin-Watson:           0.060
Prob(Omnibus):        0.000    Jarque-Bera (JB):        22.368
Skew:                 0.371    Prob(JB):                1.39e-05
Kurtosis:             2.877    Cond. No.:                6.65e+10
=====
    
```

(Both Outputted the same graph)

susceptible to these changes with higher volume, causing more volatility. Next, looking at regression analysis, we can see a correlation coefficient indicating a positive relationship. However, the R-squared value suggests that volume must thoroughly understand price movements. By using Machine Learning, we can see a range of statistics in the outputted data, with many of them not impacting our understanding of Bitcoin's volume and broader economic impacts. Next, when we use the correlation of ATMs and population in the city, we can see more about financial inclusion and the grasp this implementation has, which is not very significant in counteracting underbanked regions and going towards financial inclusion.

Discussion

Significance of Results

The quantitative analysis showcases a complex connection between cryptocurrency transaction volumes and their closing prices, further signifying the dynamic nature of the cryptocurrency market within El Salvador. The scatter plots and regression analysis show how they represent Bitcoin's susceptibility to volatility due to high transaction volumes. This volatility is critical to understanding the economic behavior of Bitcoin as a legal tender and understanding its broader implications. We evaluated 73 top cities in El Salvador and evaluated ATMs to population, in which $\frac{1}{3}$ had around 1 ATM, with most having small populations. Another $\frac{1}{3}$ had 0 ATMs with a varied population, which signifies an inability to support financial inclusion and advocate for under- or unbanked areas. Looking at the Quantitative aspect, we can see an understanding of financial inclusion, its Impact on SMEs, and Broader Economic Implications, which showcase concern from individuals and organizations worldwide, signifying unreadiness and highlighting many issues and problems that the integration of Bitcoin has.

Expanding and working on financial inclusion with the support of its economy is a concern, and SMEs having issues transitioning can be looked at as concerning.

Results Connecting to Research

This research highlights the complex implications of Bitcoin adoption on financial inclusion and SMEs, considering its broad economic impact on El Salvador's economy. The results look at all impacts and break them down into these three topics by looking at them on a Qualitative and Quantitative scale to get a holistic view. The Qualitative results are divided into three parts based on the research and sub-research questions. The Quantitative results look at financial inclusion and Broader economic impact, which also correlates with volatility, which relates to SMEs and their use of Bitcoin for day-to-day transactions and usage. These aspects directly connect the research results, broken down into three parts.

Limitations

This paper has limitations, such as the crucial limitation identified by analyzing the R-squared value from the regression model crafted. This limitation suggests that the data given and the volume were not enough predictors to predict Bitcoin price movements. This can underscore the multifaceted factors influencing cryptocurrency markets, which cannot be answered and understood through volume alone. Besides this limitation, we can see that the lack of data has not given the richest results, and it did not evaluate all the needed factors due to much of the data being behind paywalls or private government information, making it challenging to give the most accurate results. Additionally, the presence of a significant amount of technical issues within this adoption process, such as difficulties with the Chivo Wallet, indicates a limitation in the infrastructure that supports the Bitcoin integration into El Salvador, bringing

light to the limitations of primary sources of individuals using these and being impacted by this integration daily.

Implications

The implications of this paper stem from the adoption of Bitcoin in El Salvador and how it presents broader economic implications, looking more at relations with international financial institutions such as the IMF. A significant concern about macroeconomic stability and the potential for worsening socioeconomic conditions and disparities could undermine the long-term benefits that cryptocurrency interrogation could achieve. The opinion of the international crypto community is positive, but this does not translate to sustained economic development or lead to financial inclusion without having a set strategy for cryptocurrency education and infrastructure in El Salvador, as many Salvadorans disagree with this integration.

Conclusion

Impact in the Field

This study provides insight that can be pivotal to understanding what cryptocurrency will become. It provides empirical evidence on the effects of a third-world nation adopting cryptocurrency; it can impact the field significantly by setting a benchmark for other countries and strategies interested in such a path to move forward with their plans. El Salvador also showcases caution and the importance of macroeconomic stability and infrastructure readiness, which is needed for the success of similar financial initiatives. This research additionally embarks on financial inclusion, which challenges existing banks and models running for centuries, and tries to understand how the integration of digital currencies will work by looking at the broader economic impacts. It underscores aspects that can be essential for digital

currencies such as Bitcoin to have the ability to reshape the financial system and landscape around the world. It showcases its potential to fight for financial inclusion, allowing all individuals access to banking with limited needs.

Future Directions

Looking toward the future and the direction in which research could delve, the Chivo Wallet's transaction data would provide a significant amount of data to understand patterns of adoption, daily usages, business usages, and economic impacts, and further understand its ability toward financial inclusion. This data and the financial inclusion metric could shed significant light on the effectiveness of cryptocurrency in expanding financial access in El Salvador and help showcase it as a real currency, understanding its broader implications. SME impact can be combined with the given data and interviews to further understand the quantitative impact this paper wants to answer. Continuing into a mixed-method approach, which uses both quantitative and qualitative research from Chivo wallet and interviews/surveys, can help offer a richer understanding of cryptocurrencies' ability in this market and the potential to be expanded outside El Salvador. This further research can give the ability to guide policymakers and stakeholders to make initiatives to work on financial inclusion, making sure a shift to digital banking and digital sources such as Bitcoin can produce benefits for all, particularly in regions often previously marginalized by traditional banking systems.

Bibliography

- Pantin, L. P. (2023). Financial Inclusion, Cryptocurrency, and Afrofuturism. *Northwestern University Law Review*, 118(3), 621–689.
- Ecer, F., Büyükaslan, A., & Hashemkhani Zolfani, S. (2022). Evaluation of Cryptocurrencies for Investment Decisions in the Era of Industry 4.0: A Borda Count-Based Intuitionistic Fuzzy Set Extensions EDAS-MAIRCA-MARCOS Multi-Criteria Methodology. *Axioms* (2075-1680), 11(8), N.PAG. <https://doi.org/10.3390/axioms11080404>
- Omelchuk, O., Iliopol, I., & Alina, S. (2021). Features of Inheritance of Cryptocurrency Assets. *Ius Humani*, 10(1), 103–122. <https://doi.org/10.31207/ih.v10i1.233>
- Nugent, C. (2021). What El Salvador Gets from Betting on Crypto. *TIME Magazine*, 198(15/16), pp. 48–51.
- Washington, P. B., Gali, P., Rustam, F., & Ashraf, I. (2023). Analyzing the influence of COVID-19 on crypto financial markets and sentiment analysis using a deep ensemble model. *PLoS ONE*, 18(9), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0286541>
- Karush, G. E. (1978). Plantations, Population, and Poverty: The Roots of Demographic Crisis in El Salvador. *Studies in Comparative International Development*, 13(3), 59. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02686473>
- Taylor, L. (2022). The world's first Bitcoin republic. *New Scientist*, 253(3376), 14. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0262-4079\(22\)00360-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0262-4079(22)00360-8)
- Nugent, C. (2021). What El Salvador Gets from Betting on Crypto. *Time International (Atlantic Edition)*, 198(15/16), p. 48.

Aaron Klein, Adrianna Pita, et al. “Debunking the Narratives about Cryptocurrency and Financial Inclusion.” Brookings, 24 June 2023,
www.brookings.edu/articles/debunking-the-narratives-about-cryptocurrency-and-financial-inclusion/.

Best, Raynor de. “Topic: Bitcoin in El Salvador.” Statista,
www.statista.com/topics/8401/bitcoin-in-el-salvador/#topicOverview. Accessed 15 Apr. 2024.

Bitcoin ATM El Salvador – Find Bitcoin Machine Locations,
coinatmradar.com/country/64/bitcoin-atm-el-salvador/. Accessed 15 Apr. 2024.

Bitcoin USD (BTC-USD) Price History & Historical Data - Yahoo Finance,
finance.yahoo.com/quote/BTC-USD/history/. Accessed 15 Apr. 2024.

Central Intelligence Agency, Central Intelligence Agency,
www.cia.gov/the-world-factbook/countries/el-salvador/. Accessed 15 Apr. 2024.

Chivo ATM Cryptocurrency ATM Machine Producer,
coinatmradar.com/manufacture/128/chivo-atm-bitcoin-atm-producer/. Accessed 15 Apr. 2024.

“Cryptocurrency Prices, Charts and Market Capitalizations.” CoinMarketCap,
coinmarketcap.com/. Accessed 15 Apr. 2024.

“El Salvador’s Bitcoin Journey: Tracing the Impact of Cryptocurrency as Legal Tender.”
Greenbook,
www.greenbook.org/insights/focus-on-latam/el-salvadors-bitcoin-journey-tracing-the-impact-of-cryptocurrency-as-legal-tender. Accessed 15 Apr. 2024.

Engler, Andrés. “El Salvador Plans to Offer Crypto-Based Loans for SMEs.” CoinDesk Latest

Headlines RSS, CoinDesk, 11 May 2023,

www.coindesk.com/business/2022/01/21/el-salvador-plans-to-offer-crypto-based-loans-for-smes/.

Ethereum USD (ETH-USD) Price History & Historical Data - Yahoo Finance,

finance.yahoo.com/quote/ETH-USD/history/. Accessed 15 Apr. 2024.

“Meta Platforms, Inc. (Meta) Stock Price, News, Quote & History.” Yahoo! Finance, Yahoo!, 15

Apr. 2024, finance.yahoo.com/quote/META/.

Population of Cities in El Salvador 2024,

worldpopulationreview.com/countries/cities/el-salvador. Accessed 15 Apr. 2024.

“Which Countries Use the US Dollar?” Stripe,

stripe.com/resources/more/which-countries-use-the-us-dollar-heres-a-complete-list#:~:text=El%20Salvador%3A%20El%20Salvador%20switched,in%202001%20for%20economic%20stability. Accessed 15 Apr. 2024.

Deep down in the crypto-dip. (2022). *Economist*, 445(9322), 30.

Ghitis, F. (2022). El Salvador’s Bitcoin Gamble Just Went Bust. *World Politics Review*

(Selective Content), 1–4.

Sparkes, M. (2022). El Salvador revamps bitcoin system. *New Scientist*, 253(3373), 8.

Náñez Alonso, S. L., Echarte Fernández, M. Á., Sanz Bas, D., & Pérez Rico, C. (2024). El

Salvador: an analysis of the monetary integration law and the bitcoin law. *Brazilian*

Journal of Political Economy / Revista de Economia Política, 44(1), 189–209.

<https://doi.org/10.1590/0101-31572024-3459>

Taylor, L. (2022). The world's first bitcoin republic. *New Scientist*, 253(3376), 14.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0262-4079\(22\)00360-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0262-4079(22)00360-8)

Taylor, L. (2022). El Salvador's crypto gamble goes sour. *New Scientist*, 255(3392), 16.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0262-4079\(22\)01105-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0262-4079(22)01105-8)

Taylor, L. (2021). El Salvador's adoption of bitcoin hits further problems. *New Scientist*,

252(3358), 16. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0262-4079\(21\)01915-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0262-4079(21)01915-1)

Alvarez, F., Argente, D., & Van Patten, D. (2023). Are cryptocurrencies currencies? Bitcoin as legal tender in El Salvador. *Science*, 382(6677), 1375.

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.add2844>

Nugent, C. (2022). Why El Salvador's Bukele Is Doubling Down on Bitcoin Despite the Crypto Crash. *Time.com*, 1.

Sparkes, M. (2021). Bitcoin versus central banks. *New Scientist*, 251(3352), 16.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/s0262-4079\(21\)01635-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0262-4079(21)01635-3)

Gerstner, L. (2022). What You Need to Know About CRYPTO. *Kiplinger Personal Finance*, 76(7), 42–48.

Rodriguez, M. (2022). Conducting Effective Legal Research on Cryptocurrency. *AALL Spectrum*, 26(5), 17–19.

Stinson, R. (2021). Should You Invest in Crypto? *Kiplinger Personal Finance*, 75(10), 66.